

CULTURAL AVOIDANCE SCALE IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING: VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY STUDY

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to develop a scale to measure the level of avoidance of foreign language learners towards the target culture. The study group consisted of 500 freshmen at Atatürk University who study in education, science, social and health sciences. In the study, an item pool consisting of 69 questions was prepared as a data collection tool. The face validity of the scale was done with the researchers and 3 specialist academicians teaching foreign languages, the items that were repeated and difficult to understand were eliminated, and some items were changed in terms of language and expression, and a form consisting of 39 questions was reached. After the opinions of experts were taken in line with the content validity, a draft scale of 28 questions was applied to the study group by eliminating 11 items. The data obtained from the study were analyzed by item analysis, exploratory and confirmatory factor analysis methods. At the end of the study, it was understood that the Cultural Avoidance Scale in Foreign Language Learning consisting of 28 items was a reliable and valid scale.

Keywords: foreign language learning, cultural avoidance, scale development

1. Introduction

Language is a means of understanding among people. Language is a magical being that is so multifaceted that we cannot think of it at once, that its other aspects occur when looking from different perspectives and whose secrets we cannot solve today (Aksan, 1995:11). Language is not just a system of words and their rules of use. It is a symbolic expression of a culture's way of thinking. Each culture's way of thinking is determined

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by the formation process of this culture that lasts for centuries, so languages are not different in terms of words, but mainly these processes of formation and therefore ways of thinking (Titiz 1997: 12-15).

Since language is the basis of culture, everything written and spoken in the language of a nation falls into the concept of culture (Kaplan, 2007: 151). No area of society is language independent. *"It is a whole with the literature, philosophy, art and technique of the society; thoughts, the way of comprehension, customs and traditions are interconnected to language and cannot be separated from language. Transfer from one generation to the next can be done through a statement, but only the language achieves this. The language, thought, way of thinking and traditions of a society whose culture has changed also change"* (Akarsu, 1998: 88-89).

When it comes to culture, it is not only language and literature but there is also art such as music, painting, dance and architecture (Kaplan, 2007:26). Each language has its own proverbs and idioms, and difficulties in translating them into another language show that each language is the work and mirror of the world of the labor of the heart with different possibilities (Ünalán, 2010:17). The cultures of nations are not just written and oral works. The customs and traditions that nations follow together are the basis of their national personalities (Kaplan, 2007:25). These elements are unifying inside and distinguishing when compared to other nations.

Foreign language teaching is of significant importance for developing countries. Since a language cannot be considered independent of the culture of the society that speaks that language, the culture of the language learned encompasses those who learn this language inevitably (Ünalán, 2010: 64). Since language is the carrier and the survivor of culture, learning a foreign language is significantly equivalent to learning the culture of the target language. Foreign language is based on "learning" and "acquiring" activities. Even though learning is conscious, the acquisition can develop unconsciously. The student, without realizing it, enters the field of influence of the culture s/h is in, and s/he may attempt to learn the culture of the target language, sometimes as an admiration to the culture, and sometimes as a condition that s/he should know.

According to Ozil, learning foreign languages is a gateway to various societies' perspectives, thought and value systems (1991: 96). Learning a foreign language means understanding a different world and a foreign culture. Understanding and deciphering a stranger gives the student a wealth of knowledge and thought, expanding his/her view of the world (Tapan, 1995: 156). Learning a foreign language is an important process in which not only learning the words, grammatical structure and speaking style of a language but also cultural learning of that language takes place. The one who learns a foreign language should learn the cultural data of the target language that are necessary for communication and to acquire communication skills (Demircan, 1990: 26).

Tseng (2002: 2) stated that to be successful in learning a foreign language, the language learner should also have knowledge about the culture of the language s/he has learned, and for example, knowing the culture of the language learned by a person reading any reading text in a foreign language will help him understand the text he reads

more easily and quickly. It can be said that knowing the culture of the target language makes it easier to learn a foreign language.

It is emphasized by Fink and Mairitsch (2003) that learning the rules of the target language is not sufficient in foreign language learning, the social, cultural, political and economic structure of the language should be learned and students should be aware of the culture of the language they learn. In this context, foreign language teaching aims to open up to multiculturalism on the one hand, and to live together in peace and tranquillity in multicultural communities on the other hand. Today, the main purpose of this foreign language learning understanding, more specifically, intercultural communication-oriented approach, is to gain intercultural communication ability (Işık, 1996: 7).

In its declaration in 2000, the Council of Europe stated that the sociocultural knowledge of the foreign language being taught should be given first, and these categories are daily life (table manners, food, beverage, official holidays, working hours, leisure activities, hobbies, reading habits, common sports), living conditions (living standards, home conditions, socioeconomic status), interpersonal relationships (class structure and inter-class relations, female-male relations, family structures and relations, intergenerational relations, political and religious group relations) values, beliefs and behaviors (social class, working communities, income level, traditions, art, music, etc.) language, social traditions (punctuality, gifts, dresses, prohibitions, rules, etc.), customary behaviors (religious rules, birth and marriage traditions, festivals, ceremonies and celebrations).

In foreign language learning, it has been expressed in many studies that knowing and learning the culture of the target language will contribute to learning the target language well (Khuwaileh, 2000; Kramsch, 2009; Kumaravadivelu, 2008; Moloney, 2007; Paige et al., 2003). Therefore, issues such as the interest of the learner towards the target culture or the desire to learn the target culture or avoiding the culture of the target language appear as situations that will facilitate or make language learning easier. It is an important issue to reveal the viewpoints of individuals learning foreign languages on the target culture and the effects of their proximity or distance to the learning of the target language, and to measure this situation. In this study, it is aimed to develop a valid and reliable measurement tool to determine whether foreign language learners avoid the target culture.

2. Method

In this part of the study, detailed information about research design, study group, data collection tool, data analysis techniques and procedures followed in the process has tried to be given.

2.1 Research Pattern

In the study, a mixed-methods model was created by following the qualitative and quantitative research processes sequentially. The research process is shown in Figure 1.

Firstly, the study was carried out by reviewing the relevant literature, and at the same time, an item pool was created by seeking the opinions of academics who are experts in the subject. After the item pool was created, expert opinions were consulted and the face and content validity of the items in the pool were examined, and the draft scale was reached as a result of the analyses.

Figure 1: Research Process

Content validity studies were carried out primarily on the draft scale; then, it was applied to a group of 8 undergraduates and the parts that were missing and students had difficulties in understanding were determined, and final corrections were made on the draft scale and it was made ready to be applied to the main group. The draft scale was applied to 500 freshmen studying at the undergraduate level in education, social, science and health sciences. The validity and reliability analyzes of the data obtained from the draft scale were completed, and the scale was finalized. Looking at the course of the research, it is understood that it started with qualitative processes and completed with quantitative processes. In mixed-method research, such research is called exploratory sequential pattern (Creswell, 2014). Therefore, this research was carried out following the principles of the exploratory pattern.

In the qualitative dimension of the research, literature review and interview technique were used. Cognitive constructs of experts about cultural avoidance were tried to be understood through the interviews (Johnson & Christensen, 2014; Sevim, 2019). In the quantitative part of the study, a correlation study was carried out to determine the cultural avoidance levels of students in foreign language learning by applying the draft scale to the study group (Fraenkel & Wallen, 2006; Kaptan, 1998).

2.2 The Study Group

The study group of this study, which was carried out to develop the Cultural Avoidance Scale in Foreign Language Learning, is the freshmen studying at Atatürk University in the fall semester of 2019-2020 academic year. In order to ensure maximum diversity while forming the study group, 500 students studying in the fields of education, science, social sciences and health sciences were reached by random sampling method.

Table 1: The Study Group

Field	Gender		Total
	Female	Male	
Educational Sciences	54	66	120
Science	61	59	120
Social Sciences	63	77	140
Health Sciences	56	64	120
Total	234	266	500

Considering the principle of volunteering in participating in the study, firstly, students were informed about the draft scale, and the draft scale was applied to the students who wanted to participate in the study. Information about the study group is presented in the table above.

Analyzing Table 1, it is seen that 46.8% of the study group is female and 53.2% is male students. While 120 students from education, science and health sciences each participated in the research, 140 students from social sciences agreed to evaluate the draft scale.

2.3 Data Collection

"Cultural Avoidance Scale in Foreign Language Learning" developed by the researchers was used as a data collection tool in the research. The scale is composed of 3 dimensions and 28 items, namely "Cultural Elements", "Willingness to Learn Culture" and "Interest in Culture". The scale was prepared in 7-point Likert style. Table 2 can be addressed to see clearly the rating of the levels of participation and disagreement except for the strongly agree, strongly disagree and neutral.

Table 2: Rating of the 7-point Likert Scale

Strongly Disagree	Somewhat Disagree		Neither Agree nor Disagree	Somewhat Agree		Strongly Agree
1	2	3	4	5	6	7

While the highest score that participants can get from the scale is 196, the lowest score is 28. As the score increases, it means that the level of cultural avoidance of the participant in learning a foreign language is high.

2.4 Procedure

The scientific procedure followed in the preparation of the Cultural Avoidance Scale in Foreign Language Learning can be expressed as follows:

- The first stage in the preparation of the scale is the literature review. At this stage, in order to determine the characteristics of the role of cultural avoidance in foreign language learning, scientific researches on the importance of culture in foreign language teaching both domestic and abroad were examined, and the items that could be included in the item pool were emphasized.

- An item pool consisting of 63 questions was prepared by examining the scientific researches reached.
- Although it is understood that the items in the item pool are theoretically collected under three dimensions, as the exploratory factor analysis will be applied to the draft scale, the items in the item pool are accepted as collected under a single dimension and applied to the participants.
- The items in the item pool consisting of 63 items were examined by researchers and three experts teaching foreign languages in terms of face validity, and the number of items was reduced to 39. The purpose of doing the face validity is to determine what the candidate items to be included in the scale measure in terms of the target audience (DeVellis, 2003: 57). Face validity is determined by taking the opinions of the field experts or participants in order to have a common opinion about whether the items that can be included in the scale measure the researched structure (Şencan, 2005: 743). The items in the item pool were evaluated by the researchers and the field expert in terms of their intelligibility, length and in terms of being easy to answer.
- The item pool consisting of 39 items was handled in terms of intelligibility through a focus group interview conducted by the researchers, each item was presented to the views of 8 students in the group, and some linguistic changes were made on the candidate items as a result of their feedback.
- 39 items whose face validity were done were handled in terms of content validity by 10 academics specialized in Turkish language education and 4 academics specialized in educational sciences; and it was evaluated by giving feedback as “usable, must be corrected and removed”.
- Lawshe technique (as cited in Yurdağül, 2005) was used to determine the content validity rates of candidate items. In Lawshe technique, the content validity ratio is calculated by taking one less than the ratio of the number of experts making the “usable” decision for each item in the draft scale to half of the total number of experts:

$$CVR = \frac{NK}{N/2} - 1$$

- In this formula, CVR is the content validity ratio; NK is the number of experts who say that the item can be used; N is the total number of experts. If the result is a value below 0 and 0, that item is removed from the draft scale. Items with a value above 0 are evaluated considering minimum values converted into tables by Veneziano and Hooper (as cited in Yurdağül, 2005). These minimum values also give the statistical significance of the item (Sevim, 2019: 572). Table 3 shows the minimum values for the content validity rates:

Table 3: Minimum Values for Content Validity Ratios at 0.05 Significance Level

Number of Experts	Minimum Value	Number of Experts	Minimum Value
5	0,99	13	0,54
6	0,99	14	0,51
7	0,99	15	0,49
8	0,78	20	0,42
9	0,75	25	0,37
10	0,62	30	0,33
11	0,59	35	0,31
12	0,56	40	0,29

In the study, the opinions of 14 experts were taken for the draft scale. According to Table 3, the minimum content validity rate for 14 experts is 0.51. The content validity ratios of 39 items in the draft scale are shown in Table 4:

Table 4: Content Validity Rates of the Items in the Draft Scale

Item No	CVR value	Item No	CVR value
1*	0,28	21	0,85
2	0,71	22*	0,42
3	0,57	23	0,85
4*	0,42	24	1
5	0,71	25*	0,42
6	0,85	26	0,71
7	0,71	27	0,57
8	1	28	1
9	0,85	29	0,71
10	0,71	30*	0,42
11*	0,42	31	0,71
12	1	32	1
13	0,71	33	0,71
14*	0,42	34*	0,42
15	0,71	35	0,71
16*	0,28	36	1
17	0,71	37	0,57
18	0,85	38	0,71
19	0,71	39*	0,42
20*	0,42		

Looking at Table 4, it is understood that items numbered 1, 4, 11, 14, 16, 20, 22, 25, 30, 34, 39 are smaller than the content validity ratio (0.51). Therefore, these 11 items were not removed from the scale.

Following the calculation of the content validity ratios, the scale was applied to the target audience by giving the final form to the draft scale containing 28 items with the arrangements made in line with expert opinions.

2.5 Data Analysis

After the face and content validity processes were completed, the draft scale, which was finalized, was applied to 500 students. The item discrimination indices of the data obtained from the Cultural Avoidance Scale in Foreign Language Learning were primarily examined. Then, exploratory factor analysis was done on the data set, and attention was paid to have factor loads of at least 0.30 and above (Büyüköztürk, 2002). In order to check the suitability of the data set for exploratory factor analysis, the results of the KMO test, one of the spherical tests, were examined (Tavşancıl, 2010). Cronbach Alpha coefficient was examined for the sub-dimensions of the scale and total reliability. Confirmatory factor analysis was also performed to confirm the dimensions reached by exploratory factor analysis (Büyüköztürk, Çokluk-Bökeoğlu & Köklü, 2011).

3. Findings

3.1 Findings from Item Analysis

In determining the discrimination of the scale items, the t values of each item between 27% super and subgroups and significance levels were examined. The results of the analysis are shown in Table 5.

Table 5: 27% T-Test Results Between Sub-Supergroups and Item Total Correlations

	Group	N	Mean	SD	t	FTC	p
M1	Supergroup (27%)	135	6,38	,879		0,7765	,000
	Subgroup (27%)	135	3,61	1,595			
M2	Supergroup (27%)	135	6,21	,985		0,6673	,000
	Subgroup (27%)	135	4,03	1,722			
M3	Supergroup (27%)	135	6,05	1,040		0,7988	,000
	Subgroup (27%)	135	3,77	1,657			
M4	Supergroup (27%)	135	6,07	,998		0,7765	,000
	Subgroup (27%)	135	3,57	1,231			
M5	Supergroup (27%)	135	6,31	,807		0,7065	,000
	Subgroup (27%)	135	4,21	1,704			
M6	Supergroup (27%)	135	6,77	,424		0,6206	,000
	Subgroup (27%)	135	3,30	1,054			
M7	Supergroup (27%)	135	6,38	,820		0,7946	,000
	Subgroup (27%)	135	3,64	1,472			
M8	Supergroup (27%)	135	6,21	,839		0,5932	,000
	Subgroup (27%)	135	4,08	1,563			
M9	Supergroup (27%)	135	4,64	,684		0,6510	,000
	Subgroup (27%)	135	3,03	1,329			
M10	Supergroup (27%)	135	4,18	,742		0,7574	,000
	Subgroup (27%)	135	2,89	,950			
M11	Supergroup (27%)	135	4,51	,622		0,7099	,000
	Subgroup (27%)	135	2,97	1,224			
M12	Supergroup (27%)	135	6,41	,761		0,6478	,000
	Subgroup (27%)	135	3,59	1,174			
M13	Supergroup (27%)	135	4,59	,559		0,6926	,000
	Subgroup (27%)	135	3,25	,960			
M14	Supergroup (27%)	135	6,36	,837		0,6064	,000
	Subgroup (27%)	135	3,44	1,177			

M15	Supergroup (27%)	135	6,54	,647		0,8557	,000
	Subgroup (27%)	135	3,62	1,254			
M16	Supergroup (27%)	135	6,48	,721		0,8848	,000
	Subgroup (27%)	135	3,43	1,102			
M17	Supergroup (27%)	135	4,46	,647		0,5844	,000
	Subgroup (27%)	135	3,20	1,093			
M18	Supergroup (27%)	135	6,67	,507		0,7265	,000
	Subgroup (27%)	135	3,93	1,413			
M19	Supergroup (27%)	135	4,51	,849		0,6705	,000
	Subgroup (27%)	135	3,02	,885			
M20	Supergroup (27%)	135	6,46	,673		0,7067	,000
	Subgroup (27%)	135	3,67	1,235			
M21	Supergroup (27%)	135	6,48	,721		0,7335	,000
	Subgroup (27%)	135	3,56	1,272			
M22	Supergroup (27%)	135	3,70	,937		0,7008	,000
	Subgroup (27%)	135	2,34	1,063			
M23	Supergroup (27%)	135	4,79	,635		0,6081	,000
	Subgroup (27%)	135	3,48	1,089			
M24	Supergroup (27%)	135	6,43	,784		0,5115	,000
	Subgroup (27%)	135	3,74	1,210			
M25	Supergroup (27%)	135	6,59	,559		0,7406	,000
	Subgroup (27%)	135	3,38	1,003			
M26	Supergroup (27%)	135	5,77	1,764		0,6065	,000
	Subgroup (27%)	135	3,75	1,234			
M27	Supergroup (27%)	135	6,54	,647		0,5395	,000
	Subgroup (27%)	135	3,46	1,191			
M28	Supergroup (27%)	135	6,30	,843		0,7185	,000
	Subgroup (27%)	135	3,48	1,178			

As seen in Table 5, according to the results of independent samples t test, 28 items were found to be significant at the desired level.

3.2 Findings from Exploratory Factor Analysis

In order to test the suitability of the sample size for factor analysis, Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Test was applied to the data set, and the results are shown in Table 6.

Table 6: KMO Test Results

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		,836
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	35698,155
	df	378
	Shallow	,000

On analyzing Table 6, KMO value is 0.83, and the sample size was found to be good for factor analysis (Leech, Barrett, Morgan, 2005; Tavşancıl, 2010).

After the KMO Test, the total variance explained related to the scale items was examined. Results for this process are shown in Table 7.

Table 7: Total Variance Explained

Component		Initial Eigen Values			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
		Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
dimension0	1	15,173	54,190	54,190	15,173	54,190	54,190
	2	6,093	21,759	75,950	6,093	21,759	75,950
	3	2,783	9,938	85,888	2,783	9,938	85,888
	4	1,269	4,534	90,422	1,269	4,534	90,422
	5	,775	2,768	93,189			
	6	,566	2,021	95,210			
	7	,378	1,349	96,559			
	8	,167	,597	97,156			
	9	,142	,508	97,664			
	10	,100	,358	98,022			
	11	,085	,303	98,325			
	12	,080	,284	98,610			
	13	,070	,252	98,861			
	14	,059	,212	99,073			
	15	,043	,153	99,227			
	16	,038	,134	99,361			
	17	,035	,126	99,487			
	18	,029	,104	99,590			
	19	,023	,083	99,674			
	20	,020	,072	99,746			
	21	,019	,068	99,814			
	22	,014	,051	99,864			
	23	,011	,040	99,905			
	24	,008	,029	99,934			
	25	,008	,028	99,961			
	26	,006	,020	99,981			
	27	,003	,012	99,993			
	28	,002	,007	100,000			

On looking at Table 7, it was understood that 4 factors were recommended for exploratory factor analysis, and the contribution of these 4 factors to the total variance was 90%, 422. However, considering the contribution of each factor to the total variance, the contribution to the total variance decreased after the first three factors. This situation is also observed in the Scree Plot Graph in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Scree Plot Graph

On analyzing the Scree Plot Graph in Figure 2, it is understood that the contribution of the factors after the fourth point to the total variance decreases similarly and the scree has a plot appearance after the fourth point. Therefore, based on the Scree Plot Graph in Figure 2, the factor number of the scale was decided to be 3, and the items were re-analyzed, and varimax rotation was done so that the factor number was 3 (Cattel, 1966; Özdamar and Dinçer, 1987). The total variance explained after the rotation is presented in Table 8.

Table 8: Total Variance Explained After Rotation

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings			
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	
dimension0	1	15,173	54,190	15,173	54,190	54,190	10,092	36,044	36,044	
	2	6,093	21,759	6,093	21,759	75,950	9,688	34,602	70,646	
	3	2,783	9,938	85,888	2,783	9,938	85,888	4,268	15,242	85,888
	4	1,269	4,534	90,422						

Analyzing the Table 8, it is understood that the contribution of 3 factors to variance is 85.888%. The distribution of the scale items to these three factors are shown in Table 9.

Table 9: Rotated Components Matrix

	Component		
	1	2	3
M4	,852	,183	,121
M5	,852	,184	,174
M12	,852	,166	,138
M2	,850	,182	,174
M11	,847	,183	,169
M9	,844	,208	,155
M10	,842	,185	,199
M6	,841	,186	,169
M3	,840	,200	,184
M7	,812	,169	,140

M8	,799	,096	,224
M16	,158	,856	,157
M18	,175	,854	,148
M15	,189	,852	,173
M24	,181	,850	,174
M23	,176	,842	,165
M21	,146	,840	,183
M20	,203	,838	,180
M14	,204	,836	,131
M22	,172	,833	,142
M19	,192	,823	,129
M27	,197	,198	,809
M25	,186	,156	,808
M13	,132	,059	,782
M1	,126	,047	,776
M26	,227	,286	,690
M28	,230	,295	,684
M17	,145	,465	,580

When we look at Table 9, it is seen that 11 items are in the first dimension, 10 items are in the second dimension and 7 items are in the third dimension. When the contents of the scale items that come together in each dimension are analyzed, it was deemed appropriate to name the first dimension as Cultural Elements, the second dimension as a Willingness to Learn Culture, and the third dimension to Interest in Culture.

3.3 Findings from Confirmatory Factor Analysis

As a result of the exploratory factor analysis applied to the Cultural Avoidance Scale in Foreign Language Learning, the scale showed a three-factor structure, there were 11 items in the first factor, 10 items in the second factor and 7 items in the third factor, and it was understood that the scale consists of 28 items. In order to test the model of the scale, which has a three-factor structure, the sample size must be at least ten times the number of items (Kline 2005). The scale consisting of 28 items was tested on 500 participants and the required sample width was reached.

Figure 3: Path Diagram and t Values of the Three Factor Model of Cultural Avoidance Scale in Foreign Language Learning

In the path diagram in Figure 3, firstly, t values related to the explanation levels of latent variables for observed variables were checked, and all items were found to be significant at the level of 0.01. When looking at the error variances related to the items, it was observed that the error variances of M 9 (0.86) and M 22 (0.88) were high, but it was decided to keep them in the model because of the t values being significant.

Analyzing the scale's path diagram, p value is significant at the level of 0.01; X^2 / df ratio of 2.83; RMSEA value was found to be 0.39. Data on other fit indices are provided in Table 10.

Table 10: Fit Indices and Limit Values of Fit Indices of Cultural Avoidance Scale in Foreign Language Learning

	χ^2	Df	χ^2/df	GFI	AGFI	NNFI	CFI	RMSR	SRMSR	RMSEA
MASMÖ	1080,61	381	2,83	0,91	0,89	0,94	0,96	0,073	0,053	0,039
Limit Values			≤ 5	≥ 0,85	≥ 0,80	≥ 0,80	≥ 0,80	≤ 0,10	≤ 0,10	≤ 0,05

GFI: goodness-of-fit index; AGFI: adjusted goodness of fit index; NNFI: non-normed fit index; CFI: comparative fit index; RMSR: root mean square residual; SRMR: standardized root mean square residual; RMSEA: root mean square error of approximation.

When Table 10 is examined, it is seen that the fit index values are GFI = 0.91, AGFI = 0.89, NNFI = 0.94, CFI = 0.96, RMSR = 0.073, SRMSR = 0.053 and RMSEA = 0.039.

In Table 11, Cronbach alpha, mean, standard deviation and corrected item total correlation (CITC) values related to the sub-dimensions of the scale are given.

Table 11: Values Related to the Sub-Dimensions of the Scale

	N	Mean	S	CITC
Cultural Elements	M2	5,23	1,536	,539
	M3	5,07	1,639	,539
	M4	5,05	1,330	,428
	M5	5,25	1,545	,592
	M6	5,33	1,519	,566
	M7	5,25	1,612	,552
	M8	5,25	1,453	,503
	M9	3,80	1,274	,409
	M10	3,59	,920	,441
	M11	3,80	1,056	,452
	M12	5,28	1,367	,448
	Cronbach Alpha			.890
Willingness to Learn Culture	M14	5,16	1,428	,615
	M15	5,31	1,392	,836
	M16	5,23	1,419	,895
	M18	5,41	1,357	,772
	M19	3,73	1,067	,463
	M20	5,33	1,356	,793
	M21	5,32	1,415	,845
	M22	3,08	1,073	,545
	M23	4,13	1,027	,400
	M24	5,30	1,348	,784
Cronbach Alpha			.937	
Interest in Culture	M1	5,03	1,665	,451
	M13	3,89	,879	,475
	M17	3,80	,992	,497
	M25	5,18	1,481	,494
	M26	4,88	1,636	,481
	M27	5,22	1,444	,480
	M28	5,25	1,419	,483
Cronbach Alpha			.850	

When Table 11 is analyzed, it is understood that the internal consistency coefficients for each sub-dimension are 0.890 (Willingness to Learn Culture), 0.937 (Cultural Elements) and 0.850 (Interest in Culture), respectively. The total Cronbach Alpha coefficient of the

scale is 0.930 and the high Cronbach Alpha coefficient related to the sub-dimensions indicates the reliability of the scale (Baykul, 1979; Özdamar, 1999).

4. Results and Discussion

In this scale development study conducted to determine the level of avoidance of foreign language learners towards the culture of the target language, firstly, research about the effect of culture in foreign language learning were examined (Aliakbari, 2004; Alptekin, 1993; Bada, 2000; Baker, 2011; Chamberlain, 2005; Çakır, 2006; Emiroğlu, 2016; Gülcü, 2010; Iriskulova, 2012; Sancak, 2009; Thanasoulas, 2001), and then a pool of 63 items was created by discussing with the relevant academics and students in the foreign language learning process. Face validity was made by the researchers and three experts teaching foreign languages, and the number of items was reduced to 39. These 39 items were presented to students' views through a focus group interview conducted under the direction of the researchers, and changes were made to the items with the feedback received. The Lawshe technique was applied to determine the content validity rates of candidate items, and these 39 items were subjected to expert opinion and re-arranged to be 28 items, taking into account the minimum values recommended by Veneziano and Hooper (cited in Yurdagül, 2005).

Cultural Avoidance Scale in Foreign Language Learning was applied to 500 freshman studying foreign languages, and statistical procedures such as item analysis, exploratory factor analysis and confirmatory factor analysis were performed on the obtained data.

In the item analysis process, it was examined whether there was a significant difference between the average scores of 27% sub- and supergroups, and all items were found to be significant at the level of 0.00. With this process, it was seen that 28 items in the scale were significant at the desired level. After item analysis, exploratory factor analysis was applied to the data set to determine the factor structure of the draft scale. According to the results of exploratory factor analysis, it was determined that the draft scale has a three-factor structure and the total variance explained was 85,888%. After Varimax rotation, the factor loads of the draft scale ranged from 0.856 to 0.580.

After the exploratory factor analysis, confirmatory factor analysis was performed to confirm the factor structure of the draft scale. In this analysis, it was seen that the error variances of M 9 (0.86) and M 22 (0.88) were high, but it was decided to keep these items in the model due to the t values being significant (Büyüköztürk, Çokluk-Bökeoğlu & Köklü, 2011). As a result of the confirmatory factor analysis, it was found that the fit indices values of the three-factor structure of the draft scale were $\chi^2 / df = 2.83$, GFI = 0.91, AGFI = 0.89, NNFI = 0.94, CFI = 0.96, RMSR = 0.073, SRMR = 0.053, RMSEA = 0.039. The fact that the X^2 / df ratio is 2.83 indicates that the model fit is perfect (Schermelel-Engel, Moosbrugger and Müller, 2003). According to Kline (2005), RMSEA's value below 0.05 indicates very close model fit indices. That the RMSEA's value is 0.039 indicates that the data compatibility of the model is excellent. The SRMR's value of 0.053 and CFI's 0.96 reveal that the model's fit indices meet the reference values (Hooper, Caughlan & Mullen,

2008; Hu & Bentler, 1999; Kline, 2005; Sümer, 2000). Considering all these fit indices, it is understood that the model data fit of the Cultural Avoidance Scale in Foreign Language Learning is in good condition.

With all analyzes, it was concluded that the final scale consists of 28 items with a three-factor structure. The first dimension is named as Cultural Elements since the items in the this dimension emphasize cultural elements, the second dimension is named as Willingness to Learn Culture as the items that come together in the this dimension express the desire to learn of foreign language, and the third dimension is named as Interest in Culture as the items in the third dimension express the interest of individuals for the target culture. There are 11 items in the Cultural Elements dimension, 10 items in the Willingness to Learn Culture dimension and 7 items in the Interest in Culture dimension. The evaluation ranges of the scores obtained from the scale are as follows: 28-84 points: Low Avoidance, 85-141 points: Moderate Avoidance, 142-196 points: High Avoidance. While the highest score that can be obtained from the scale is 196, the lowest score that can be obtained is 28. Since items 1, 6, 10, 11, 16, 26 and 28 in the scale are significantly positive, they should be coded in reverse. The final form of the Cultural Avoidance Scale in Foreign Language Learning is presented in Appendix 1.

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Appendix 1

Draft Scale	Final Scale	Cultural Avoidance Scale in Foreign Language Learning	Strongly disagree	Somewhat Disagree		Neither Agree nor Disagree	Somewhat Agree		Strongly Agree
			1	2	3	4	5	6	7
4	1	I wonder the wedding and mourning ceremonies of the culture of the target language.							
5	2	The dishes of the culture of the target language do not attract my attention.							
12	3	I do not want to watch TV series and movies that belong to the culture of the target language.							
2	4	I don't like to sing / listen to the songs of the culture of the target language in daily life.							
11	5	I do not want to learn the types of dance in the culture of the target language.							
9	6	I closely follow the political agenda of the culture of the target language.							
10	7	Religious and national holidays related to the culture of the target language do not interest me.							
6	8	Local clothing and dressing belonging to the culture of the target language do not interest me.							
3	9	I am not interested in the food / beverage types of the culture of the target language.							
7	10	I would like to learn about the prohibitions of the culture of the target language.							
8	11	The religious beliefs of people who live in the culture of the target language are effective for me to learn that language.							
16	12	I don't want to learn the culture of the language I learned.							
18	13	I do not want to participate in cultural activities related to the target language.							
15	14	The family life related to the culture of the target language does not interest me.							
24	15	Cultural elements of the target language do not interest me.							
23	16	I do research on the culture of the target language in my leisure time.							
21	17	I am content with what I know instead of learning new things about the culture of the target language.							
20	18	I fail to compare my own culture to the target language.							
14	19	I don't care about the differences between my own culture and the culture of the target language.							
22	20	I am reluctant to learn the cultural elements of the culture of the target language.							
19	21	I do not try to increase my cultural knowledge of the target language.							
27	22	I do not turn down the opportunity to visit historical sites of the culture of the target language.							

25	23	I would rather spend time at home than to participate in cultural tours of the target language.							
13	24	I do not try to learn the geography of the culture of the target language.							
1	25	I will not make an effort to investigate the living conditions of the culture of the target language.							
26	26	I do not refuse to go to the resorts of the culture of the target language.							
28	27	I avoid socializing with individuals who live in the culture of the target language.							
17	28	I do not refuse the opportunity to participate in traditional celebrations and ceremonies of the culture of the target language.							

Appendix 2

Taslak Ölçek	Nihai Ölçek	Yabancı Dil Öğrenmede Kültürel Kaçınma Ölçeği	Kesinlikle katılmıyorum		Kısmen katılmıyorum		Kararsızım		Kısmen katılıyorum		Kesinlikle katılıyorum	
			1	2	3	4	5	6	7			
4	1	Hedef dilin kültürüne ait düşün ve yas törenlerini merak ederim.										
5	2	Hedef dilin kültürüne ait yemekler dikkatimi çekmez.										
12	3	Hedef dilin kültürüne ait dizi ve sinema filmlerini izlemek istemem.										
2	4	Hedef dilin kültürüne ait şarkıları günlük hayatta söylemek/dinlemek hoşuma gitmez.										
11	5	Hedef dilin kültürüne ait dans çeşitlerini öğrenmek istemem.										
9	6	Hedef dilin kültürüne ait siyasi gündemi yakından takip ederim.										
10	7	Hedef dilin kültürüne ait dinî ve millî bayramlar ilgimi çekmez.										
6	8	Hedef dilin kültürüne ait yöresel giyim ve kuşam ilgimi çekmez.										
3	9	Hedef dilin kültürüne ait yiyecek/içecek türleri ilgimi çekmez.										
7	10	Hedef dilin kültürüne ait yasakları öğrenmek isterim.										
8	11	Hedef dilin kültürünü yaşayan insanların dinî inançları o dili öğrenmemde etkilidir.										
16	12	Öğrendiğim dilin kültürünü de öğrenmek istemem.										
18	13	Hedef dil ile ilgili kültürel etkinliklere katılmak istemem.										

15	14	Hedef dilin kültürüne ait aile hayatı ilgimi çekmez.							
24	15	Hedef dile ait kültürel unsurlar ilgimi çekmez.							
23	16	Boş zamanlarımda hedef dilin kültürü ile ilgili araştırmalar yaparım.							
21	17	Hedef dilin kültürüne ait yeni şeyler öğrenmektense bildiklerimle yetinirim.							
20	18	Kendi kültürümle hedef dile ait kültürü karşılaştırmakta başarısızım.							
14	19	Kendi kültürümle hedef dile ait kültür arasındaki farklılıkları önemsemem.							
22	20	Hedef dilin kültürüne ait kültürel unsurları öğrenmede isteksiz davranırım.							
19	21	Hedef dile ait kültürel birikimimi artırmaya çalışmam.							
27	22	Hedef dilin kültürüne ait tarihî yerleri gezme fırsatını geri çevirmem.							
25	23	Hedef dile ait kültürel gezilere katılmaktansa evde vakit geçirmeyi tercih ederim.							
13	24	Hedef dilin kültürüne ait coğrafyayı öğrenmek için çabalamam.							
1	25	Hedef dilin kültürüne ait yaşam koşullarını araştırmak için çaba harcamam.							
26	26	Hedef dilin kültürüne ait tatil beldelerine gitme fırsatını geri çevirmem.							
28	27	Hedef dilin kültürünü yaşayan bireylerle sosyalleşmeden kaçınırım.							
17	28	Hedef dilin kültürüne ait geleneksel kutlama ve gösterilere katılma fırsatını geri çevirmem.							

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